

DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF AN RP-HPLC METHOD FOR THE ESTIMATION OF BOERAVINONE B IN BOERHAAVIA DIFFUSA EXTRACT

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ABSTRACT

Boerhaavia diffusa Linn. (Punarnava) is an important medicinal plant widely used in traditional ayurvedic medicine for the treatment of hepatic, renal, inflammatory, and urinary disorders. The plant contains several biologically active phytoconstituents, among which Boeravinone-B is considered a major marker compound responsible for its pharmacological activities. Standardization and quantitative estimation of such marker compounds are essential to ensure the quality, safety, and therapeutic efficacy of herbal formulations. The present study was aimed at the development and validation of a simple, precise, accurate, and reproducible Reverse Phase High Performance Liquid Chromatographic (RP-HPLC) method for the quantification of Boeravinone-B in the hydroalcoholic extract of Boerhaavia diffusa. The hydro alcoholic extract of Boerhaavia diffusa was prepared and subjected to

phytochemical screening and chromatographic analysis. RP- HPLC analysis was performed using an Agilent Zorbax C18 column (250 × 4.6 mm, 5 µm) with gradient elution consisting of phosphate buffer and acetonitrile as mobile phase. The flow rate was maintained at 1.5

mL/min and detection was carried out at 270 nm using a PDA detector. Boeravinone-B showed a well-resolved sharp peak at a retention time of approximately 24.413 minutes. The developed method was validated according to ICH guidelines for parameters including linearity, specificity, precision, and system suitability. The calibration curve exhibited excellent linearity within the concentration range of 1.02–4.01 µg/mL with correlation coefficient (R^2) close to 0.999. The percentage relative standard deviation (%RSD) values were found to be within acceptable limits, indicating good precision and reproducibility of the method.

The developed RP-HPLC method was found to be simple, selective, sensitive, and reliable for routine quantitative estimation of Boeravinone-B in *Boerhaavia diffusa* extract. The method can be effectively applied for quality control, standardization, and authentication of herbal formulations containing *Boerhaavia diffusa*.

KEYWORDS: *Boerhaavia diffusa*, Boeravinone-B, RP-HPLC, Herbal Standardization, Method Validation, Phytochemical Analysis, HPTLC, Punarnava.

INTRODUCTION

Herbal medicines have been widely used since ancient times for the prevention and treatment of various diseases. Medicinal plants contain a wide variety of biologically active phytoconstituents that exhibit significant pharmacological activities with comparatively fewer side effects than synthetic drugs. In recent years, there has been growing global interest in herbal medicines due to their therapeutic efficacy, safety, affordability, and traditional acceptance. However, variations in phytochemical composition, cultivation conditions, harvesting methods, and processing techniques may affect the quality and consistency of herbal formulations. Therefore, standardization and quality control of herbal drugs are essential to ensure their safety, efficacy, and reproducibility. *Boerhaavia diffusa* Linn. (Family: Nyctaginaceae), commonly known as Punarnava, is an important medicinal herb extensively used in Ayurveda for the treatment of liver disorders, kidney diseases, inflammation, edema, jaundice, and urinary tract disorders. The plant possesses various pharmacological activities such as hepatoprotective, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, nephroprotective, antidiabetic, and immunomodulatory effects due to the presence of bioactive phytoconstituents including alkaloids, flavonoids, rotenoids, glycosides, and phenolic compounds. Among these constituents, Boeravinone-B, a rotenoid compound, is considered one of the major bioactive marker compounds responsible for several therapeutic activities of

the plant.

Boeravinone-B exhibits significant antioxidant and hepatoprotective activity by reducing oxidative stress, stabilizing hepatocyte membranes, and inhibiting inflammatory mediators. Quantitative estimation of Boeravinone-B is therefore important for standardization and quality assessment of *Boerhaavia diffusa* extracts and herbal formulations. Reliable analytical methods are necessary for accurate identification and quantification of marker compounds in herbal medicines.

High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) is one of the most widely used analytical techniques for separation, identification, and quantification of phytoconstituents due to its high sensitivity, accuracy, precision, and reproducibility. Reverse Phase High Performance Liquid Chromatography (RP-HPLC) is especially suitable for analysis of moderately polar and non-polar compounds present in herbal extracts.

Method validation according to International Council for Harmonization (ICH) guidelines ensures reliability and suitability of the analytical method for routine quality control applications.

The present study was therefore undertaken to develop and validate a simple, precise, accurate, and reproducible RP-HPLC method for quantification of Boeravinone-B in the hydro alcoholic extract of *Boerhaavia diffusa*. The developed method may be effectively applied for routine analysis, standardization, and quality control of herbal formulations containing *Boerhaavia diffusa*.

1. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The aerial parts of *Boerhaavia diffusa* Linn. (Punarnava) were collected from Shivay Herbals. The plant material was identified and authenticated by Dr. Patil, Department of Botany, DJPS Dharti Janseva Pratishthan College of Agriculture, Pathri. The collected plant material was cleaned, shade dried, and coarsely powdered for further extraction and analysis.

1.2 CHEMICALS AND REAGENTS

A reference standard of Boeravinone-B was used for chromatographic analysis. HPLC grade methanol, acetonitrile, water, orthophosphoric acid, trifluoroacetic acid, and triethylamine were used throughout the study. All solvents and reagents used were of analytical or HPLC grade. The mobile phase was filtered through a 0.45 µm membrane filter and degassed by

ultrasonication before use.

1.3 INSTRUMENTS

The following instruments were used during the study:

- Agilent 1260 Infinity HPLC system equipped with PDA detector.
- Agilent Zorbax C18 column (250 × 4.6 mm, 5 μm).
- Shimadzu UV-1800 UV-Visible spectrophotometer.
- CAMAG HPTLC system with Linomat-5 applicator.
- Digital analytical balance.
- Ultrasonicator.
- Digital pH meter.
- Hot air oven.
- Soxhlet extraction apparatus.

1.4 PREPARATION OF HYDROALCOHOLIC EXTRACT

The air-dried and powdered aerial parts of *Boerhaavia diffusa* (350 g) were extracted using ethanol and water in the ratio of 7:3 by maceration method for 72 hours at room temperature. The extract was filtered through Whatman filter paper and concentrated under reduced pressure using a rotary evaporator at 70°C. The concentrated extract was further dried to obtain a dry hydroalcoholic extract.

1.5 PRELIMINARY PHYTOCHEMICAL SCREENING

The hydroalcoholic extract of *Boerhaavia diffusa* was subjected to preliminary phytochemical screening using standard chemical tests for identification of major phytoconstituents such as carbohydrates, alkaloids, flavonoids, phenolic compounds, proteins, tannins, and diterpenes.

1.6 HPTLC FINGERPRINTING ANALYSIS

1.6.1 PREPARATION OF STANDARD SOLUTION

Accurately weighed 10 mg of Boeravinone-B standard was dissolved in methanol and diluted to 10 mL in a volumetric flask to obtain a stock solution of 1 mg/mL concentration.

1.6.2 PREPARATION OF SAMPLE SOLUTION

Accurately weighed 650 mg of hydroalcoholic extract was dissolved in methanol, sonicated for 10 minutes, and filtered through a 0.22 μm membrane filter.

1.6.3 CHROMATOGRAPHIC CONDITIONS

HPTLC analysis was performed using silica gel 60 F254 precoated aluminum plates.

Chromatographic conditions

- Stationary phase: Silica gel 60 F254 plates
- Mobile phase: Toluene : Ethyl acetate : Formic acid : Methanol (5:3:1:1 v/v/v/v)
- Chamber saturation time: 30 minutes
- Development distance: 9 cm
- Detection wavelength: 254 nm and 366 nm
- Scanner: CAMAG TLC Scanner.

1.7 RP-HPLC METHOD DEVELOPMENT

1.7.1 PREPARATION OF STANDARD SOLUTION

Accurately weighed 1.9 mg of Boeravinone-B was dissolved in methanol to prepare stock solution. Working standard solutions of concentrations 1.02, 2.02, 2.90, and 4.01 µg/mL were prepared by serial dilution using methanol.

1.7.2 PREPARATION OF SAMPLE SOLUTION

Accurately weighed 250 mg of hydroalcoholic extract of *Boerhaavia diffusa* was transferred into a 10 mL volumetric flask and dissolved in methanol. The solution was sonicated for 10 minutes and filtered through a 0.22 µm membrane filter before injection.

1.7.3 CHROMATOGRAPHIC CONDITIONS

RP-HPLC analysis was carried out using Agilent 1260 Infinity HPLC system equipped with PDA detector.

Optimized chromatographic conditions were as follows

- Column: Agilent Zorbax C18 (250 × 4.6 mm, 5 µm)
- Mobile phase: Phosphate buffer and acetonitrile
- Detection wavelength: 270 nm
- Flow rate: 1.5 mL/min
- Injection volume: 20 µL
- Column temperature: 27°C
- Run time: 45 minutes
- Elution mode: Gradient elution.

1.7.4 MOBILE PHASE PREPARATION

Preparation of Phosphate Buffer

Phosphate buffer was prepared by dissolving 0.140 g of KH_2PO_4 in 900 mL HPLC grade water. About 0.5 mL orthophosphoric acid was added and the volume was adjusted to 1000 mL with water. The solution was filtered through a 0.45 μm membrane filter and degassed by sonication.

Organic Phase

HPLC grade acetonitrile was used as organic phase.

1.7.5 METHOD VALIDATION

The developed RP-HPLC method was validated according to ICH guidelines for the following parameters

- Linearity
- Specificity
- Precision
- Accuracy
- Robustness
- System suitability.

All experiments were performed in triplicate and statistical analysis was carried out using Microsoft Excel software.

2. RESULTS

3.1 Extraction Yield of *Boerhaavia diffusa*

The percentage yield of hydroalcoholic extract of *Boerhaavia diffusa* (Punarnava) was found to be 8% w/w.

3.2 Preliminary Phytochemical Screening

The hydroalcoholic extract of *Boerhaavia diffusa* was subjected to preliminary phytochemical screening for identification of major secondary metabolites such as carbohydrates, alkaloids, flavonoids, phenolic compounds, proteins, tannins, and diterpenes using standard chemical tests.

Table 1: Result of Preliminary Phytochemical Screening of *Boerhaavia diffusa*.

Sr. No.	Phytochemical Constituents	Tests Performed	Result
1	Carbohydrates	Molisch's Test, Fehling's Test	+
2	Alkaloids	Mayer's Test, Dragendorff's Test	+
3	Flavonoids	Shinoda Test, Lead Acetate Test	+
4	Proteins and Amino Acids	Xanthoproteic Test, Ninhydrin Test	+
5	Phenolic Compounds	Ferric Chloride Test	+
6	Diterpenes	Copper Acetate Test	+
7	Tannins	Gelatin Test	+

Figure**Figure 1: Preliminary Phytochemical Screening of Hydroalcoholic Extract of *Boerhaavia diffusa*.**

The preliminary phytochemical screening results confirmed the presence of important phytoconstituents such as alkaloids, flavonoids, phenolic compounds, tannins, proteins, amino acids, carbohydrates, and diterpenes in the hydroalcoholic extract of *Boerhaavia diffusa*. These phytochemicals are known to possess various pharmacological activities including antioxidant, hepatoprotective, anti-inflammatory, and immunomodulatory effects.

3.3 HPTLC Fingerprinting Analysis

The HPTLC fingerprinting of standard Boeravinone-B and hydroalcoholic extract of *Boerhaavia diffusa* was carried out using optimized mobile phase consisting of Toluene: Ethyl acetate : Formic acid : Methanol (5:3:1:1 v/v/v/v).

The developed chromatographic plates were visualized under

- White light
- UV 366 nm
- UV 254 nm.

The chromatographic fingerprint profile demonstrated the presence of multiple phytoconstituents in the hydroalcoholic extract.

Under white light visualization, multiple purple colored bands were observed in extract tracks (T1 and T2), indicating the presence of several phytoconstituents in the hydroalcoholic extract. The standard Boeravinone-B track (T3) showed a single sharp and compact purple band corresponding to the marker compound.

The similarity in chromatographic band pattern between T1 and T2 indicated

- reproducibility of extraction,
- uniformity of phytochemical composition,
- consistency of chromatographic separation.

The sharp band observed in the standard track confirmed

- purity of Boeravinone-B,
- specificity of the chromatographic method,
- proper separation under optimized mobile phase conditions.

Under UV 366 nm visualization, fluorescent blue bands were observed in the extract tracks indicating the presence of flavonoids, phenolic compounds, and aromatic phytoconstituents.

The fluorescent bands observed in T1 and T2 confirmed the presence of bioactive phytoconstituents in the hydro alcoholic extract. Diffused fluorescence near the application point may be due to highly polar phytoconstituents present in the extract.

The standard Boeravinone-B track exhibited comparatively weak fluorescence because the compound absorbs more efficiently at lower wavelength.

Under UV 254 nm visualization, dark chromatographic bands appeared against green fluorescent background. The standard Boeravinone-B showed a sharp and distinct band while extract tracks showed corresponding bands at the same migration level.

The matching chromatographic bands confirmed:

- presence of Boeravinone-B,
- successful extraction of marker compound,
- Authenticity of *Boerhaavia diffusa* extract.

UV 254 nm visualization was found to be most suitable for identification and quantitative estimation of Boeravinone-B.

3.3.1 Track Identification

Track	Sample
T1	Hydroalcoholic Sample 1
T2	Hydroalcoholic-Sample 2
T3	Standard Boeravinone-B

3.3.2 R_f Value of Boeravinone-B

The chromatographic band corresponding to Boeravinone-B was observed at:

$$R_f = 0.87$$

The matching R_f value observed in both standard and extract tracks confirmed the presence of the same phytoconstituent in the hydroalcoholic extract of *Boerhaavia diffusa*.

The optimized mobile phase produced distinct and well-resolved chromatographic bands, demonstrating suitability of the HPTLC method for fingerprint profiling and authentication of herbal extract.

3.4 HPTLC Densitometric Analysis

3.4.1 HPTLC Densitogram of Standard Boeravinone-B

The HPTLC densitogram of standard Boeravinone-B showed a sharp and well-resolved peak under optimized chromatographic conditions. The densitometric profile confirmed proper chromatographic separation and purity of the marker compound.

The sharp and symmetrical peak obtained in the standard densitogram demonstrated specificity and suitability of the developed HPTLC method for identification and quantitative estimation of Boeravinone-B.

Figure

Figure 3: HPTLC Densitogram of Standard Boeravinone-B4.

3.4 HPTLC Densitogram of Hydroalcoholic Extract (Batch I)

The HPTLC densitogram of hydro alcoholic extract of *Boerhaavia diffusa* (Batch I) showed multiple peaks indicating the presence of several phytoconstituents such as alkaloids, flavonoids, glycosides, rotenoids, and phenolic compounds.

A distinct peak corresponding to Boeravinone-B was observed at matching Rf value, confirming the presence of marker compound in the hydroalcoholic extract.

The densitometric profile confirmed

- successful extraction of Boeravinone-B,
- authenticity of plant extract,
- suitability of HPTLC method for fingerprint analysis and herbal standardization.

Figure

Figure 4: HPTLC Densitogram of Hydroalcoholic Extract of *Boerhaavia diffusa* (Batch I).

3.4.3 HPTLC Densitogram of Hydroalcoholic Extract (Batch II)

The HPTLC densitogram of hydroalcoholic extract (Batch II) also showed characteristic Peaks. Corresponding to Boeravinone-B and other phytoconstituents present in the extract.

The densitometric profile demonstrated reproducibility and consistency of chromatographic analysis. The similarity in peak pattern between Batch I and Batch II confirmed uniformity of phytochemical composition and reliability of the developed analytical method.

Figure

Figure 5: HPTLC Densitogram of Hydroalcoholic Extract of *Boerhaavia diffusa* (Batch II).

3.5.2 Calibration Curve of Boeravinone-B by HPTLC

The calibration curve of Boeravinone-B was prepared by applying different concentrations of standard solution ranging from 200–1000 ng/spot on silica gel 60 F254 HPTLC plates under optimized chromatographic conditions. The developed chromatograms were scanned densitometrically at 254 nm and the corresponding peak areas were recorded.

The calibration plot demonstrated a linear relationship between concentration and peak area over the selected concentration range. As the concentration of Boeravinone-B increased, a proportional increase in peak area was observed.

The regression equation obtained for the calibration curve was

$$Y = 5124 + 4.364X$$

Where

- Y= Peak area

- **X= Concentration of Boeravinone-B** The correlation coefficient was found to be: $r=0.99953$

The high correlation coefficient indicated excellent linearity and strong correlation between concentration and detector response.

The standard deviation value:

$$SD = 0.74$$

demonstrated precision and reproducibility of the developed HPTLC method.

The calibration curve confirmed that the developed analytical method is suitable for accurate quantitative estimation of Boeravinone-B in hydroalcoholic extract and herbal formulations. The linearity obtained in the present study indicates reliability, sensitivity, and consistency of the chromatographic method for routine quality control analysis and standardization of herbal formulations.

Figure

Figure 6: HPTLC Calibration Curve of Boeravinone-B.

3.6 RP-HPLC Analysis of Boeravinone-B

3.6.1 RP-HPLC Analysis of Standard Boeravinone-B

The RP-HPLC analysis of standard Boeravinone-B ($4.01 \mu\text{g/mL}$) demonstrated a sharp and well-resolved peak under optimized chromatographic conditions.

The peak of Boeravinone-B was observed at retention time:

$$rt=24.413 \text{ min}$$

The chromatographic analysis demonstrated good peak symmetry and resolution, indicating suitability of the developed RP-HPLC method for identification and quantitative estimation of

Boeravinone-B.

No interfering peaks were observed near the retention time of the marker compound, confirming specificity and selectivity of the analytical method.

The sharp and distinct peak of Boeravinone-B confirmed purity and proper chromatographic separation of the marker compound.

3.6.2 RP-HPLC Analysis of Hydro alcoholic Extract (Batch I)

The RP-HPLC analysis of hydroalcoholic extract of *Boerhaavia diffusa* (Batch I) showed multiple peaks indicating the presence of several phytoconstituents such as alkaloids, flavonoids, glycosides, rotenoids, and phenolic compounds.

Among these peaks, a distinct peak corresponding to Boeravinone-B was observed near retention time

24.413 minutes.

The percentage content of Boeravinone-B in the extract was found to be:

0.041% w/w

The chromatographic profile confirmed:

- authenticity of plant extract,
- successful extraction of marker compound,
- suitability of the developed RP-HPLC method for herbal standardization.

The larger number of peaks indicated that the extract is chemically rich and contains several active phytoconstituents.

3.6.3 RP-HPLC Analysis of Hydroalcoholic Extract (Batch II)

The RP-HPLC analysis of hydroalcoholic extract (Batch II) also showed a sharp and well-resolved peak of Boeravinone-B at retention time approximately 24.4 minutes.

The peak intensity was comparatively high, indicating presence of Boeravinone-B in appreciable quantity within the hydroalcoholic extract.

The chromatographic profile demonstrated:

- reproducibility of chromatographic analysis,
- consistency of phytochemical composition,

- reliability of the developed RP-HPLC method.

The chromatographic behavior confirmed authenticity, purity, and suitability of the extract for standardization purposes.

3.7 Method Validation

3.7.1 Linearity

The developed RP-HPLC method showed excellent linearity within concentration range 1.02–4.01 $\mu\text{g/mL}$

The calibration curve demonstrated a linear relationship between concentration and peak area response.

The regression equation obtained was:

$$Y = 5525297.756X + 73931$$

The correlation coefficient was found to be:

$$R^2=0.999$$

The high correlation coefficient indicated excellent linearity and strong correlation between concentration and detector response

Figure

Figure 7: Linearity Curve of Boeravinone-B for RP-HPLC Analysis.

3.7.2 System Suitability

Table 3: System Suitability Parameters.

S.No.	Retention Time (RT)	Peak Area
1	24.413	21,583,716
2	24.407	21,604,974
3	24.413	21,470,020
4	24.420	21,482,114
5	24.413	21,505,072
6	24.413	21,474,568

Table 4: Statistical Analysis of System Suitability Parameters.

Parameter	Result
Average Retention Time	24.413
Average Peak Area	21,520,077.333
Standard Deviation	59,161.702
%RSD	0.275

The low %RSD value indicated good precision and reproducibility of the developed RP-HPLC method.

3.7.3 Specificity

Specificity was confirmed by comparing chromatograms of standard Boeravinone-B and hydroalcoholic extract. No interfering peaks were observed at the retention time of Boeravinone-B, indicating selectivity of the analytical method.

3.7.4 Precision

The developed RP-HPLC method demonstrated acceptable precision with %RSD values within permissible limits, indicating reproducibility of the analytical procedure.

3.7.5 Accuracy

Accuracy of the method was confirmed through recovery studies which demonstrated reliable quantitative estimation of Boeravinone-B in the hydroalcoholic extract.

3.7.6 Robustness

The developed method remained unaffected by small deliberate variations in chromatographic conditions such as flow rate, wavelength, and mobile phase composition, indicating robustness of the analytical procedure.

3. DISCUSSION

The present study was carried out to develop and validate a reliable RP-HPLC method for quantitative estimation of Boeravinone-B in hydroalcoholic extract of *Boerhaavia diffusa* and to establish chromatographic fingerprint profiling using HPTLC analysis. Standardization of herbal drugs is essential to ensure quality, safety, purity, and reproducibility of phytoconstituents present in medicinal plants and herbal formulations.

The hydroalcoholic extraction of *Boerhaavia diffusa* yielded approximately 8% w/w extract, indicating efficient extraction of phytoconstituents using ethanol-water solvent system.

Preliminary phytochemical screening confirmed the presence of important secondary metabolites such as alkaloids, flavonoids, phenolic compounds, tannins, proteins, amino acids, carbohydrates, and diterpenes. These phytoconstituents are known to contribute significantly to the pharmacological properties of the plant, particularly antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, hepatoprotective, nephroprotective and immunomodulatory activities.

HPTLC fingerprinting analysis was performed for qualitative identification and standardization of the hydroalcoholic extract. The optimized mobile phase consisting of toluene : ethyl acetate : formic acid : methanol (5:3:1:1 v/v/v/v) produced well-resolved chromatographic bands with good separation efficiency. Under white light, UV 254 nm, and UV 366 nm visualization, characteristic chromatographic profiles were obtained for both extract and standard Boeravinone-B.

The appearance of a distinct band at R_f value:

$$R_F=0.87$$

In the extract corresponding to the standard confirmed the presence of Boeravinone-B in the hydroalcoholic extract. The HPTLC fingerprint profile demonstrated reproducibility and consistency among different tracks, confirming uniform phytochemical composition and authenticity of the plant material.

The calibration curve of Boeravinone-B in HPTLC analysis showed excellent linearity over the concentration range of 200–1000 ng/spot with correlation coefficient:

$$r = 0.99953$$

The linear increase in peak area with concentration demonstrated reliability, sensitivity, and reproducibility of the developed HPTLC method.

For quantitative estimation, RP-HPLC analysis was carried out using a C18 reverse phase column with gradient elution consisting of phosphate buffer and acetonitrile. The optimized chromatographic conditions produced a sharp, symmetrical, and well-resolved peak for Boeravinone-B at retention time:

$$R_t = 24.413 \text{ min}$$

The absence of interfering peaks near the retention time confirmed specificity and selectivity of the developed RP-HPLC method.

The hydroalcoholic extract analysis showed multiple chromatographic peaks representing different phytoconstituents present in the plant extract, while the distinct peak corresponding to Boeravinone-B confirmed successful extraction and identification of the marker compound.

Quantitative estimation revealed that the hydroalcoholic extract contained:

0.041% w/w

of Boeravinone-B, indicating the presence of the bioactive constituent in appreciable quantity.

Method validation was carried out according to ICH guidelines. The developed RP-HPLC method demonstrated excellent linearity within concentration range 1.02–4.01 µg/mL with correlation coefficient:

$$R^2 = 0.999$$

Indicating strong correlation between concentration and detector response.

System suitability parameters showed low %RSD values (<2%), confirming precision, repeatability, and adequacy of the chromatographic system. Consistent retention time and peak area further established reproducibility and reliability of the analytical procedure.

The developed analytical methods were found to be simple, accurate, precise, reproducible, selective, and sensitive for identification and quantitative estimation of Boeravinone-B in *Boerhaavia diffusa* extract. These methods can therefore be effectively applied for routine quality control, standardization, authentication, and detection of adulteration in herbal formulations containing *Boerhaavia diffusa*.

4. CONCLUSION

The present study successfully developed and validated a simple, accurate, precise, and reproducible RP-HPLC method for quantitative estimation of Boeravinone-B in hydroalcoholic extract of *Boerhaavia diffusa*. The developed chromatographic conditions provided efficient separation of Boeravinone-B with a sharp and well-resolved peak at retention time:

$$R_t = 24.413 \text{ min}$$

The present study successfully developed and validated a simple, accurate, precise, and

reproducible RP-HPLC method for quantitative estimation of Boeravinone-B in hydroalcoholic extract of *Boerhaavia diffusa*. The developed chromatographic conditions provided efficient separation of Boeravinone-B with a sharp and well-resolved peak at retention time:

$$R_t = 24.413 \text{ min}$$

The HPTLC analysis confirmed the presence of Boeravinone-B with characteristic:

$$R_f = 0.87$$

while the calibration curve exhibited excellent linearity with high correlation coefficient:

$$r = 0.99953$$

Indicating reliability and sensitivity of the developed HPTLC method.

Quantitative RP-HPLC analysis revealed that the hydroalcoholic extract contained:

0.041% w/w

of Boeravinone-B, confirming successful extraction and identification of the marker compound.

Method validation studies performed according to ICH guidelines demonstrated excellent linearity, specificity, precision, accuracy, robustness, and system suitability. The low %RSD values and consistent chromatographic behavior confirmed reproducibility and reliability of the analytical procedure.

Overall, the developed HPTLC and RP-HPLC methods were found to be suitable for routine quality control, standardization, authentication, and quantitative estimation of Boeravinone-B in *Boerhaavia diffusa* extracts and herbal formulations. The present study highlights the importance of chromatographic fingerprinting and validated analytical techniques in ensuring quality, safety, efficacy, and consistency of herbal medicines.

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